

Software at NASA: Lightning Breakout 2C

Infrastructure as code, and web and cloud applications

Data repository software (e.g. infrastructure software, cloud services, software environments)

Archiving software (in a FAIR manner, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-022-01710-x>)

Explore solar wind models
in three dimensions

Space Weather in the Cloud

Accessible to all, anywhere

Lowering cost and development time

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MSIS
Atmosphere Model

Explore atmospheric
composition and profiles
through time

<https://swx-trec.com>

Vehicle
Environment
Coupling and
Trajectory
Response

Drag coefficient calculated
from a spacecraft's
geometry and its
surrounding environment

LIVEDst
CU space weather prediction

Predict solar storm
intensity in real time

LiveWire
Geolectric field prediction

Real-time maps of
geoelectric and
geomagnetic fields

SWx TREC Model Staging Platform

Separable/Modular Architectures Backend

- Big Data stays in the cloud
- Scalable on-demand compute
- Infrastructure as code

Frontend

- Web-based user interface
- No local installation headaches
- Anywhere, with any device

Benefits

- 3D interactivity with large data
- Deploy ML models for scientists (not just a paper for them anymore, it is real!)
- Serverless APIs, costs us \$0 for empirical model interfaces (nice free tiers from cloud providers)

hostess: Lightweight Distributed Resource Management and Data Processing in Python

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<https://github.com/MillionConcepts/hostess/>

 Million Concepts

hostess is a general-purpose utility and administration library that provides lightweight, Pythonic interfaces to distributed resources, system processes, and Python internals. It includes high-level modules with special functionality for working with AWS EC2 instances and S3 buckets, and a framework (called station) for workflow coordination / orchestration.

hostess reduces syntactic headaches and boilerplate while still allowing low-level manipulation, with an emphasis on fitting intuitively and idiomatically into common data science and scientific analysis workflows.

```
from hostess.aws.s3 import Bucket

# initialize a bucket object
bucket = Bucket("my_extant_bucket")

# copy a file from s3 to local
bucket.get("README_REMOTE.md", "README_LOCAL_COPY.md")

# copy multiple files from local to s3
# automatically runs multithreaded
bucket.put(["README_LOCAL_1.md", "README_LOCAL_2.md"],
           ["README_REMOTE_1.md", "README_REMOTE_2.md"])

# read the file from s3 into a variable
data = bucket.read("README_REMOTE.md")

# glacier an object on s3
bucket.freeze("README_REMOTE_1.md")

# index the contents of an s3 bucket into a dataframe
# includes: key, size, and storage class
index = bucket.df()

# remove files from s3
bucket.rm(["README_REMOTE.md", "README_REMOTE_2.md"])
```


CSIRO's EASI Cloud Platform

Earth Analytics Science Innovation

Accelerating Innovation – Enhancing Engagement

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[More information](#)

The EASI Ecosystem

Open & CSIRO Data

Publish Tools & Workflows for researchers & industry

Workflow automation tools which integrate with the deployed applications

Supported and Scalable Production Applications

Jupyter and VS Code Python, R, ...

Custom tools and libraries

Researcher driven

Continental, multi-decadal, multiple satellite EO data analytics

Leveraging Cloud and Infrastructure as Code

"The masses of satellite data, open-source tools..., cloud computing, [EASI] has been a game changer"

Dr Nagur Cherukuru

A simple, generic API for timeseries data applicable across SMD

Jon Vandegriff, JHU / APL
Robert S. Weigel, George Mason University
Jeremy Faden, Cottage Systems
Sandy Antunes, JHU / APL

Full Presentation

10.5281/zenodo.11114385

Github Organization

<https://github.com/hapi-server>

Imagine accessing ANY time series
data with a single API.

Each panel came
from different server
and is easily plotted
in a single client.

Higher dimensional
data is supported.

Project Site

<https://hapi-server.org>

YouTube

<https://www.youtube.com/@hapiserver9929>

Heliophysics Application Programmer's Interface

→ no Heliophysics idioms: data model is just numbers vs. time

Interoperability

Uniform access greatly simplifies analysis of distributed data.

Reasons to Adopt

- **many data sources already available via HAPI**
Helio, Planetary, in US, Europe, Canada, also NSF and NOAA are interested
- **clients already exist for access and display**
- **easy to implement server from the spec**
(or use existing server: Python, Java, node.js)
- **active development community** (weekly meetings) and clients written outside the dev team
- **recommended as official standard by COSPAR**

Talk 5

WITHDRAWN

Unlocking the Solar System: Introducing the NASA

Planetary Data System (PDS) Web API

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Why a web API ? To easily find the Planetary science data and metadata, **across nodes and agencies, for web browsing and science analysis.**

How ?

Start from a well curated archive described in XML files following **PDS4 Information model** standard.

A **working group meets monthly** to elaborate/discuss the RESTful interface.

Development is **0.5 FTE/year** (3 developers available) (started 2020)

3 main features: **revolve** identifiers, **search** using complex queries and **crawl** the archive.

The implementation target has evolved from a distributed architecture to a centralized **on-the-cloud** deployment.

What (now) ?

A **robust, very versatile RESTful API**, transparently exposing the rich PDS4 Information Model.

OpenAPI specification, Java Spring-boot server, ANTLR query parser, OpenSearch back-end.

40+ millions products available.

Demonstrations with science use cases in Jupyter Notebooks, connecting to community tools client side (pywwt, geopandas, leaflet, Astropy, PDS Viewer...).

<https://pds.nasa.gov/api/search>

What's next ?

Moving now to MCP, with OpenSearch serverless.

A **python client library** abstracts away the hassle of URL handling, query syntax or pagination management as well as the complexity of the PDS4 information model.

This development is meant to be a **collaborative** platform where PDS data engineers can meet the expectations of researchers.

How to keep software executable for decades

By Samuel Grayson grayson5@illinois.edu

Has this ever happened to you?

- It works on my machine
- It worked yesterday
- Python: can't find module Numpy but I just installed it
- Conda: Solving environment: failed
- DockerHub changed their mind and deleted my images
- GitHub goes the way of Google Code?

Isn't this solved by ____?

- Docker

How to combine VM image A with image B
 Conda solve depends on libc patch version

Version	Date	Soname	Change Log	Backward Compat.	Added Symbols	Removed Symbols
2.37	2023-02-01	0/1/2/6	changeLog	99.65%	3 new	0
2.35	2022-02-03	0/1/2/6	changeLog	99.96%	4 new	0
2.34	2021-08-02	0/1/2/6	changeLog	96.85% added 3 objects	182 new	24 removed

Docker Hub changed their retention policy

Conda-forge drops pkgs for old OS

```

10
11 2023-08-24: Bumping Minimum MacOS version to 10.13
12 ~~~~~
13
14 We will bump the minimum MacOS version from 10.9
15 (released in Oct. 2013, end-of-life since
16 Dec. 2016) to 10.13 (released Sept. 2017, end-of-life
17 since Dec. 2020). The main reason we
18 managed to support 10.9 this long at all, is that
    
```

Conda repro failed (5 yrs)
 Old package removed

```

$ conda create -y --name r_3.2.1 -c conda-forge r=3.2.1
Solving environment: ...working... failed

PackagesNotFoundError: The following packages are not available from current channels:

- r=3.2.1

Current channels:

- https://conda.anaconda.org/conda-forge/linux-64
- https://conda.anaconda.org/conda-forge/noarch
- https://repo.anaconda.com/pkgs/main/linux-64
- https://repo.anaconda.com/pkgs/main/noarch
- https://repo.anaconda.com/pkgs/r/linux-64
- https://repo.anaconda.com/pkgs/r/noarch

To search for alternate channels that may provide the package you're
looking for, navigate to

https://anaconda.org

and use the search bar at the top of the page.
    
```

Docker build fails (4 yrs)
 Internet resource no longer accessible

```

1 FROM debian:stretch
2 RUN apt-get update && apt-get install python
    
```


What we really need

- Use build-from-source package managers (Spack, Nix, Guix)
- From-source is more composable than machine/container images
- Software Heritage
 - Collect, preserve, and share open-source SW
 - Public, long-term funding plan
- SW Carpentries-style lesson
 - In preparation: <https://github.com/charmoniumQ/reproducibility-carpentry>
 - Please provide feedback
- Be more specific than “reproducible”

Authentication and Authorization in .NET

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